

**WEIGHTED COMPOSITION OPERATORS $(1 + \epsilon)\varphi_r$
ON BERGMAN TYPE SPACES $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ WITH DOUBLE
WEIGHTED $(z + \epsilon)$**

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Abstract

This study investigates the boundedness, compactness, essential norm and the Schatten class of weighted composition operators $(1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}$ on Bergman type spaces $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ with double weight $(z + \epsilon)$. Let $X = (1 + \epsilon) \in H(\mathbb{D})$: $(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r} : A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ is bounded. For some regular weights $(z + \epsilon)$, the researcher obtains that $X = H^\infty$ if and only if φ_r is a finite Blaschke product.

Keywords: Weighted composition operator, weighted Bergman space, double weight.

1. Introduction

Let $\mathbb{D}$ be the open unit disk in the complex plane, and $H(\mathbb{D})$ the class of all functions analytic on $\mathbb{D}$. Let φ_r be an analytic self-map of $\mathbb{D}$ and $(1+\epsilon) \in H(\mathbb{D})$. Juntao Du, Songxino Li and Yecheng Shi [21]. The researcher intends to make few specific changes. The weighted composition operator, denoted by $(1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}$, is defined on $H(\mathbb{D})$ by

$$((1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}f^2)(z) = (1 + \epsilon)(z)f^2(\varphi_r(z)), f^2 \in H(\mathbb{D}).$$

For $-1 < \epsilon < \infty$, $H^{1+\epsilon}$ denotes the Hardy space, which consisting of all functions $f^2 \in H(\mathbb{D})$ satisfied

$$\|f^2\|_{H^{1+\epsilon}}^{1+\epsilon} = \sup_{0 < \epsilon < \infty} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} |f^2(1 - \epsilon)e^{i\theta}|^{1+\epsilon} d(\theta) < \infty.$$

As usual, H^∞ is the set of bounded analytic functions in $\mathbb{D}$.

The researcher says that μ is a weight, when μ radial and positive on $\mathbb{D}$. Suppose that $(z + \epsilon)$ is an integrable weight on $(0,1)$. Let $\widehat{z + \epsilon}(1 - \epsilon) \int_{1-\epsilon}^1 (z + \epsilon)(1 + \epsilon)d(1 + \epsilon)$ for $0 < \epsilon < \infty$. The researcher says that $z + \epsilon$ is regular, denoted by $(z + \epsilon) \in \mathcal{R}$, if there is a constant $C > 0$ depending on $z + \epsilon$, such that

$$\frac{1}{C} < \frac{\widehat{z + \epsilon}}{\epsilon(z + \epsilon)(1 - \epsilon)} < C, \text{ when } 0 < \epsilon < \infty.$$

The researcher gives that $z + \epsilon$ is rapidly increasing, denoted by $(z + \epsilon) \in I$, if

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\widehat{z + \epsilon}(1 - \epsilon)}{\epsilon(z + \epsilon)(1 - \epsilon)} = \infty.$$

Let

$$v_{\alpha, \beta}(1 - \epsilon) = \epsilon^\alpha \left(\log \frac{e}{\epsilon} \right)^\beta.$$

After a calculation, The researcher gives the following typical examples of regular and rapidly increasing weights, see [11], for example.

(i) When $\alpha > -1$ and $\beta \in \mathbb{R}, v_{\alpha,\beta} \in \mathcal{R}$;

(ii) When $\alpha = -1$ and $\beta < -1, v_{\alpha,\beta} \in I$ and $\left| \sin \left(\log \frac{1}{\epsilon} \right) \right| v_{\alpha,\beta}(2+\epsilon) \in I$.

In [10], Peláez introduced the set of double weights, denoted by $\widehat{\mathcal{D}}$, which includes $I \cup \mathcal{R}$. The researcher says that $(z + \epsilon) \in \widehat{\mathcal{D}}$ if there is a constant $C > 0$ such that $\widehat{z + \epsilon}(1 - \epsilon) < C(\widehat{z + \epsilon}) \left(\frac{2-\epsilon}{2} \right)$, when $0 < \epsilon < \infty$. The researcher should remark that the most part of the results see[21], which presented in the context of regular and rapidly increasing weights, continue to hold for the wider class $\widehat{\mathcal{D}}$. More details about $I, \mathcal{R}$ and $\widehat{\mathcal{D}}$ can be seen in[10,11,13].

For $-1 < \epsilon < \infty$ and $(z + \epsilon) \widehat{\mathcal{D}}$, the weighted Bergman space $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ is the space of $f^2 \in H(\mathbb{D})$ for which

$$\|f^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}^{1+\epsilon} = \int |f^2(z)|^{1+\epsilon} (z + \epsilon)(z) dA(z) < \infty,$$

Where $dA(z) = \frac{1}{\pi} dx dy$ is the normalized Lebesgue area measure on $\mathbb{D}$. When $(z + \epsilon)(1 + \epsilon) = (-\epsilon)^\alpha (\alpha > -1)$, the space $A_\alpha^{1+\epsilon}$ becomes the classical weighted Bergman space $A_\alpha^{1+\epsilon}$. the researcher refers [3,7,20] and references therein. In respects, the Hardy $H^{1+\epsilon}$ is the limit of $A_\alpha^{1+\epsilon}$ as $\alpha \rightarrow -1$. But it is a rough estimate since most of the finer function- theoretic properties of the classical weighted Bergman space $A_\alpha^{1+\epsilon}$ can not carry over to the Hardy space $H^{1+\epsilon}$. the researcher knows, $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ induced by regular weighted have similar properties with $A_\alpha^{1+\epsilon}$. But many results see [21] show that spaces $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ induced by rapidly increasing weighted, lie “closer” to $H^{1+\epsilon}$ than any $A_\alpha^{1+\epsilon}$.

In [4], Čuckovič and Zhao characterized the boundedness and compactness of weighed composition operators mapping on Bergman space $A_\alpha^{1+\epsilon}$ by using Berezin transform. The researcher investigates weighted composition operators between different Bergman spaces and Hardy spaces in [5]. In [13],

peláez and Rättyä characterized the Schatten class of Toeplitz operator is a positive Borel measure on $\mathbb{D}$ and the reproducing kernel of the Bergman space $A_{z+\epsilon}^2$ when $(z + \epsilon) \in \widehat{\mathcal{D}}$. In [18], Zhao and Hou proved that, for $A_\alpha^{1+\epsilon}$ the finite Blaschke product is the only composition symbol that the induced weighted composition operator is bounded if and only if the weighted sympl defines a bounded multiplication operator. The similar result for Hardy space $H^{1+\epsilon}$ can be seen in [21]. Motivated by [4,5,13], under the assumption that $(z + \epsilon) \in \widehat{\mathcal{D}}$ and μ is a positive Borel measure, the researcher investigates the boundedness, compactness and essential and norm of $(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}: A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_\mu^{1+2\epsilon}$ and the Schatten class of $(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}: A_{z+\epsilon}^2 \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^2$. Motivated by [18], the researcher gets that, for some $(z + \epsilon)_* \in \mathcal{R}$, $X = H^\infty$ if and only if φ_r is a finite Blaschke prouduct. Here

$$X = \{1 + \epsilon: (1 + \epsilon) \in H(\mathbb{D}) \text{ and } (1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}: A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \text{ is bounded}\}$$

Throughout this paper, the letter C will denote constants and may differ from one occurrence to the other. The notation $A \lesssim B$ means that there is a positive constant C such that $A \leq CB$. The The notation $A \approx B$ means $A \lesssim B$ and $B \lesssim A$. The researcher formulated and shows several auxiliary results which will be used in the proofs of main results see [21].

2-some Lemmas

Lemma 1. Assume that $(z + \epsilon) \in \widehat{\mathcal{D}}$, $0 \leq \epsilon \leq 1$ and $(z + \epsilon)(1 - \epsilon) = \int_{1-\epsilon}^1 s(z + \epsilon)(s) \log \frac{s}{1-\epsilon} ds$. Then the following statements hold.

(i) $(z + \epsilon)_* \in (1 - \epsilon) \approx \epsilon(\widehat{z + \epsilon})(1 - \epsilon)$ as $(1 - \epsilon) \rightarrow 1$;

(ii) there are $1 < a < b < +\infty$ and $0 \leq \delta < 1$, such that

$$\frac{(z+\epsilon)_*(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^a} \text{ is decreasing on } [\delta, 1] \text{ and } \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{(z+\epsilon)_*(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^a} = 0; \tag{1}$$

$$\frac{(z+\epsilon)_*(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^{(1+\epsilon)}} \text{ is increasing on } [\delta, 1] \text{ and } \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{(z+\epsilon)_*(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^{(1+\epsilon)}} = \infty; \tag{2}$$

(iii) $(z + \epsilon)_* (1 - \epsilon)$ is decreasing on $[\delta, 1]$ and $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} (z + \epsilon)_* (1 - \epsilon) = 0$.

Proof. By [13, Lemmas A and 9] and [1,19] in [11], (i) and (ii) hold. (iii) follows by (ii) and $(z + \epsilon)_* (1 - \epsilon) = \frac{(z+\epsilon)_* (1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^\alpha} \epsilon^\alpha$.

Remark 1. The researcher observes that $z = 0$ is the logarithmic singular point of $(z + \epsilon)_*$. SO, for any fixed $r_0 \in (0,1)$, we have $(z + \epsilon)_* (1 - \epsilon) \approx \epsilon(\widehat{z + \epsilon})(1 + \epsilon)$ for $r_0 \leq r < 1$. For simplicity, suppose $(z + \epsilon)_*$ and $\widehat{z + \epsilon}$ radial, that is, $(z + \epsilon)_*(z) = (z + \epsilon)_*(|z|)$ and $\widehat{z + \epsilon}(z) = \widehat{z + \epsilon}(|z|)$ for all $z \in \mathbb{D}$.

Suppose $\mathbb{T}$ is the boundary of $\mathbb{D}$ and $I \subset \mathbb{T}$ is an interval. The Carleson square $S(I)$ can be defined as

$$S(I) = \{(1 - \epsilon)e^{it} : e^{it} \in I, |I| \leq \epsilon < -1\},$$

where $|I|$ denotes the Lebesgue measure of I . For convenience, for each $a \in \mathbb{D} \setminus \{0\}$, the researcher defines

$$I_{1+\epsilon} = \left\{ e^{i\theta} : \left| \arg \left((1 + \epsilon)e^{-i\theta} \right) \right| \leq \frac{1 - |1 + \epsilon|}{2} \right\},$$

and denote $S(1 + \epsilon) = S(I_{1+\epsilon})$. By (26) in [10], when $(z + \epsilon) \in \widehat{\mathcal{D}}$, the researcher has

$$z + \epsilon(S(1 + \epsilon)) \approx (z + \epsilon)_*(1 + \epsilon), \text{ for all } (1 + \epsilon) \in \mathbb{D} \text{ and } |1 + \epsilon| \geq \frac{1}{2}. \tag{3}$$

The following lemma is a straight result of [10, Lemma 3.1](or [11, Lemma 2.4])

Lemma 2. Suppose $(z + \epsilon) \in \widehat{\mathcal{D}}$ and $-1 < \epsilon < \infty$. There exists $\gamma_0 > 0$, if $\gamma > \gamma_0$, the researcher has $\left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z) \right| \approx \frac{1}{(z+\epsilon)S(1+\epsilon)} \frac{1}{1+\epsilon}$

$\left\| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)} \right\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}} \approx 1$, when $(1 + \epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}$, $z \in S(1 + \epsilon)$, and

$$\lim_{|1+\epsilon| \rightarrow 1} \sup_{|z| \leq 1-\epsilon} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z) \right| = 0, \text{ when } 1 < \epsilon < -1.$$

Here and hence forth,

$$F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z) = \left(\frac{1-|1+\epsilon|^2}{1-(\bar{z}+\epsilon)z} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon} \frac{1}{(z+\epsilon(S(1+\epsilon)))^{\frac{1}{1+\epsilon}}}.$$

For simplicity, the researcher always assume that $(-\frac{1}{2} + 3\epsilon)$ is large enough so that Lemma 2 holds when mention the function $F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}$.

For a given Banach space X of analytic fuctions on $\mathbb{D}$, appositve Borel measure μ on $\mathbb{D}$ is called a $q -$ Carleson measure for X , if the identity operator $Id: X \rightarrow L^{1+2\epsilon}(z)$ is bounded. By [10, Theorem 3.3], when $(z + \epsilon) \in \widehat{\mathbb{D}}$, a Borel measure μ on $\mathbb{D}$ is a $q -$ Carleson measure for $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ if and only if

$$\sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \frac{\mu(S(1+\epsilon))}{(z+\epsilon)(S(1+\epsilon))^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}}} < \infty.$$

Moreover, $\|Id\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}} \approx \sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \frac{\mu(S(1+\epsilon))}{(z+\epsilon)(S(1+\epsilon))^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}}}$. the following lemma.

Lemma 3. Suppose $(z + \epsilon) \in \widehat{\mathbb{D}}$, μ is a positive Borel measure μ $\mathbb{D}$. Let $-1 < \epsilon \leq 2\epsilon < \infty$. For some (equivalently for all) Large enough $(-\frac{1}{2} + 3\epsilon)$, the researcher has $\|Id\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}} \approx \sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \frac{\mu(S(1+\epsilon))}{(z+\epsilon)(S(1+\epsilon))^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}}} \approx$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \int_{S(1+\epsilon)} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z) \approx \\ & \sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z). \end{aligned}$$

Here Id is the identity operator.

Proof. By Lemma 2, the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\mu(S(1+\epsilon))}{(z+\epsilon)(S(1+\epsilon))^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}}} \approx \int_{S(1+\epsilon)} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z) \leq \\ & \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z), \text{ when } (1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}. \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

So,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \frac{\mu(S(1+\epsilon))}{(z+\epsilon)(S(1+\epsilon))} \frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon} \\ & \approx \sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \int_{S(1+\epsilon)} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z) \\ & \approx \sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z). \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2 and [10, Theorem 3.3](also see [11, Theorem 2.1]), the researcher obtains

$$\int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z) \lesssim \|Id\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}} \approx \sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \frac{\mu(S(1+\epsilon))}{(z+\epsilon)(S(1+\epsilon))} \frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}.$$

The proof is complete.

Lemma 4. Suppose $-1 < \epsilon \leq 2\epsilon < \infty$, $(z + \epsilon) \in \widehat{\mathcal{D}}$, μ is a positive Borel measure on $\mathbb{D}$, and $-\frac{1}{2} + 3\epsilon$ is large enough. Let $-\frac{1}{2} < \epsilon < 0$ and

$$N_{1-\epsilon}^* = \sup_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z).$$

If μ is a q -Carleson measure for $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$, then $\mu_r = \mu / \mathbb{D} \setminus (1 - \epsilon)\mathbb{D}$ is also a q -Carleson measure for $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$, where $(1 - \epsilon)\mathbb{D} = \{z \in \mathbb{D} : |z| < (1 - \epsilon)\}$. Moreover, there is a $C > 0$, such that

$$\sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \frac{\mu(S(1+\epsilon))}{(z+\epsilon)(S(1+\epsilon))} \frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon} \leq C N_{1-\epsilon}^*. \tag{5}$$

Proof. It is obvious that $\mu_{(1+\epsilon)}$ is a q -Carleson measure for $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$. Let

$$N_{(1-\epsilon)} = \sup_{|1+\epsilon| \leq (1-\epsilon)} \frac{\mu(S(1+\epsilon))}{(z+\epsilon)(S(1+\epsilon))} \frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}.$$

When $|1 + \epsilon| \leq 1 - \epsilon$, $\frac{\mu(S(1+\epsilon))}{(z+\epsilon)(S(1+\epsilon))} \frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon} < N_{(1-\epsilon)}$ is obvious. When $|1 + \epsilon| < 1 - \epsilon$,

letting $k = \text{int} \left(\frac{1-|1+\epsilon|}{\epsilon} \right) + 1$, there exists $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k \in \mathbb{D}$ such that $S(1+\epsilon) \cap \mathbb{D} \setminus (1-\epsilon)\mathbb{D} \subset \cup_{i=1}^k S((1+\epsilon)_i)$ and $|(1+\epsilon)_i| = (1+\epsilon)$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$. By Lemma 1, the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{(1-\epsilon)}(S(1+\epsilon)) &\leq \sum_{i=1}^k \mu(S(1+\epsilon)_i) \leq N_{(1+\epsilon)} \sum_{i=1}^k (z+\epsilon) S(1+\epsilon)_i)^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}} \\ &\lesssim N_{(1-\epsilon)} \left(\frac{1+|1+\epsilon|}{\epsilon} + 1 \right) (z+\epsilon)_* (1-\epsilon)^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}} \\ &\approx N_{(1-\epsilon)} \left(\frac{1+|1+\epsilon|}{\epsilon} + 1 \right) (\epsilon)^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}} \widehat{z+\epsilon} (1-\epsilon)^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}} \\ &\leq N_{(1-\epsilon)} \left(\left(\frac{\epsilon}{1-|1+\epsilon|} \right)^{\frac{3\epsilon}{1-\epsilon}} + \left(\frac{\epsilon}{1-|1-\epsilon|} \right)^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}} \right) (1-|1+\epsilon|)^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}} \widehat{z+\epsilon} (1+\epsilon)^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}} \\ &\lesssim N_{(1-\epsilon)} (z+\epsilon) (S(1+\epsilon))^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}} \end{aligned}$$

So, there exists $C > 0$, such that

$$\frac{\mu_{(1+\epsilon)}(S(1+\epsilon))}{(z+\epsilon) (S(1+\epsilon))^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}}} \leq CN_{(1-\epsilon)}.$$

By(4), the researcher has $N_{(1-\epsilon)} \lesssim N_{(1-\epsilon)}^*$. Therefore, (5) holds. The proof is complete.

The following lemma can be proved in standard way (see, for example, Theorem 3.11 in [3]).

Lemma 5. Suppose $-1 < \epsilon, \epsilon > 0, (z+\epsilon) \in \widehat{\mathbb{D}}$ and μ is a positive Borel measure. If $T: A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}$ is linear and bounded, then T is compact if and only if whenever $\{f_k^2\}$

is bounded in $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ and $f_k^2 \rightarrow 0$ uniformly on compact subsets of $\mathbb{D}$, $\lim_{k \rightarrow 0} \|f_k^2\|_{L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}} = 0$. The following lemma can be found in [18] without a proof. For the benefits of the readers, will prove it.

Lemma 6. Let φ_r be an analytic self-map of $\mathbb{D}$. Then φ_r is a finite Blaschke product if and only if $\lim_{|z+\epsilon|\rightarrow 1} |\varphi_r(z + \epsilon)|=1$.

Proof. The sufficiency of the statement is obvious. Next the researcher shows the necessity.

Suppose $\lim_{|z+\epsilon|\rightarrow 1} |\varphi_r(z + \epsilon)|=1$. Let $(F - C) \subset \mathbb{D}$ be compact. Then there exists $0 < r < 1$ such that $(-C) \subset (1 - \epsilon)\overline{\mathbb{D}}$, where $(1 - \epsilon)\overline{\mathbb{D}} = \{z \in \mathbb{D} : |z| \leq (1 - \epsilon)\}$. Since $\lim_{|z+\epsilon|\rightarrow 1} |\varphi_r(z + \epsilon)|=1$, there is a $0 < t < 1$ such that for all $|z| > t$, the researcher has $|\varphi_r(z)| > (1 - \epsilon)$. Therefore, $\varphi_r^{-1}(F - C) \subset t\overline{\mathbb{D}}$. By the continuity of φ_r , $\varphi_r^{-1}(F - C)$ is closed. So, $\varphi_r^{-1}(F - C)$ is compact. By the subsection 7.1.3 of [17], φ_r is proper. By the subsection 7.3.1 of [17], φ_r is a finite Blaschke product. The proof is complete.

3 Main Results and proofs

Theorem 1. Assume $(z + \epsilon) \in \mathcal{D}$, $-1 \leq \frac{\epsilon}{2} < \epsilon < 0$, $(1+\epsilon): \mathbb{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is a measurable function, φ_r is an analytic self-map of $\mathcal{D}$, and μ is a positive Borel measure on $\mathbb{D}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \approx \\ & \sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(\varphi_r(z)) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} \|(1 + (z))\|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By lemma 2, the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned} & \sup_{(1 + \epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(\varphi_r(z)) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} \|(1 + \epsilon)(z)\|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z) \\ & \lesssim \|(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon}. \end{aligned}$$

Let $v(F - C) = \int_{\varphi_r^{-1}(E)} |(1 + \epsilon)(z)|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z)$ for all Borel set $(F - C)$. For all $f^2 \in A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$, letting $z + \epsilon = \varphi_r(z)$, by lemma 3 the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r} f^2\|_{L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} &= \int_{\mathbb{D}} |f^2(\varphi(z))|^{1+2\epsilon} |(1 + \epsilon)(z)|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z) \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{D}} |f^2(z + \epsilon)|^{1+2\epsilon} dv(z + \epsilon) \\
 &= \|f^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \leq \|Id\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+2\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\nu}^{1+2\epsilon}} \|f^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \\
 &\lesssim \|f^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z + \epsilon) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} dv(z + \epsilon).
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{6}$$

Making the changing of variable $z + \epsilon = \varphi_r(z)$, the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z + \epsilon) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} dv(z + \epsilon) &= \int_{\mathbb{D}} dv(z + \epsilon) = \\
 \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(\varphi_r(z)) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} \|(1 + \epsilon)(z)\|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z).
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof is complete.

Let X and Y be Banach spaces. Recall that the essential norm of linear operator $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is defined by

$$\|T\|_{e, X \rightarrow Y} = \inf \{ \|T - k\|_{X \rightarrow Y} : K \text{ is compact from } X \text{ to } Y \}.$$

Obviously $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is compact if and only if $\|T\|_{e, X \rightarrow Y} = 0$.

Theorem 2. Assume $(z + \epsilon) \in \widehat{\mathcal{D}}$, $-1 \leq \frac{\epsilon}{2} < \epsilon < 0$, $(1 + \epsilon): \mathbb{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is a measurable function, φ_r is an analytic self-map of $\mathcal{D}$, and μ is a positive Borel measure on $\mathbb{D}$. If $(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}: A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}$ is bounded, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}\|_{e, A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} &\approx \limsup_{|1+\epsilon| \rightarrow 1} \\
 \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(\varphi_r(z)) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} \|(1 + \epsilon)(z)\|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z).
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Since $(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}: A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}$ is bounded, $(1 + \epsilon) \in L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}$ and $\|1 + \epsilon\|_{L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}} \leq \|(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}$. **Upper estimate of** $\|(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}\|_{e, A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon}$. Suppose $f(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f_k^2 z^k \in H(\mathbb{D})$. For $\epsilon \in \mathbb{N}$, let

$$K_\epsilon f^2(z) = \begin{cases} \sum_{k=0}^{\epsilon} f_k^{\widehat{2}} z^k, & \epsilon > 0; \\ \sum_{k=0}^{\epsilon} \left(1 - \frac{k}{\epsilon + 1}\right) f_k^{\widehat{2}} z^k, & \epsilon = 0, \end{cases}$$

and $R_\epsilon = Id - K_\epsilon$.

By [19, proposition 1 and Corollary 3], when $0 < \epsilon < \infty$, K_ϵ is bounded uniformly on $H^{1+\epsilon}$.

By [6], $\|K_\epsilon\|_{H^1 \rightarrow H^1} \leq 1$. So, when $\epsilon \geq 0$, there is a $C = C(1 + \epsilon)$ such that

$$\|K_\epsilon f^2\|_{A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}^{1+\epsilon} \leq C \int_0^1 (z + \epsilon)(1 + \epsilon) d(1 + \epsilon) \int_0^{2\pi} \|f^2(1 + \epsilon)e^{i\theta}\|^{1+\epsilon} d\theta \leq C \|f^2\|_{A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}^{1+\epsilon},$$

$$\|R_\epsilon\|_{A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}} = \|Id - K_\epsilon\|_{A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}} \leq 1 + \|K_\epsilon\|_{A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}} \leq C + 1. \tag{7}$$

By Lemma 5 and Cauchy’s estimate, $f^2 \rightarrow f_k^{\widehat{2}} z^k$ is compact on $A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$.

Therefore, $K_\epsilon: A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ is compact. So, the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned} & \| (1 + \epsilon) C_{\varphi_r} \|_{e, L_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \\ &= \| (1 + \epsilon) C_{\varphi_r} (K_\epsilon + R_\epsilon) \|_{e, A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \\ &\leq \| (1 + \epsilon) C_{\varphi_r} R_\epsilon \|_{e, A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \end{aligned}$$

For any fixed $0 < r < 1$, by (6) the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned} \| (1 + \epsilon) C_{\varphi_r} R_\epsilon f^2 \|_{L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+\epsilon} &= \int_{\mathbb{D} \setminus (1-\epsilon)\mathbb{D}} |R_\epsilon f^2(z + \epsilon)|^{1+2\epsilon} dv(z + \epsilon) + \\ &\int_{(1-\epsilon)\mathbb{D}} |R_\epsilon f^2(z + \epsilon)|^{1+2\epsilon} dv(z + \epsilon), \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Where v is defined in the proof of the proof of Theorem 1, that is, for every

Borel set $(F - C) \in \mathbb{D}$. $v(F - C) = \int_{\varphi^{-1}(F-C)} |(1 + \epsilon)(z)|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z)$.

Let $(z + \epsilon)_{\epsilon\epsilon} = \int_0^1 (1 + \epsilon)^\epsilon (z + \epsilon)(1 + \epsilon)d(1 + \epsilon)$. Since $B_z^{z+\epsilon}(\xi) = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{(\xi z)^\epsilon}{2(z+\epsilon)_{2\epsilon+1}}$ is the reproducing Kernel of $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ (see [14,16] for example), the researcher has

$$|R_\epsilon f^2(z + \epsilon)| = |\langle R_\epsilon f^2, B_{z+\epsilon}^\omega \rangle_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2}| = |\langle f^2, R_\epsilon B_{z+\epsilon}^\omega \rangle_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2}| \approx \|f^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}} \|R_\epsilon B_{z+\epsilon}^\omega\|_{H^\infty}.$$

Here $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2}$ is the inner product induced by $\|\cdot\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2}$ and $\|\cdot\|_{H^\infty}$ is the norm of the bounded analysis function space on $\mathbb{D}$. When $|z + \epsilon| \leq (1 - \epsilon)$, the researcher has

$$\|R_\epsilon B_{z+\epsilon}^\omega\|_{H^\infty} \leq \frac{1}{\epsilon} \sum_{k=1}^\infty \frac{k(1-\epsilon)^{k-1}}{2\omega_{2k+1}} + \sum_{k=\epsilon+1}^\infty \frac{(1-\epsilon)^k}{2\omega_{2k+1}}.$$

By [16, Lemma 6], $\sum_{k=1}^\infty \frac{k(1-\epsilon)^{k-1}}{2\omega_{2k+1}}$ is convergent and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=\epsilon+1}^\infty \frac{(1-\epsilon)^k}{2\omega_{2k+1}} = 0$.

So, for all $\epsilon > 0$, there is a $N = N(\epsilon, z + \epsilon, 1 - \epsilon)$, such that

$$|R_\epsilon B_{z+\epsilon}^\omega| < \epsilon, \text{ for all } |z + \epsilon| \leq (1 - \epsilon) \text{ and } \epsilon > N.$$

So, for all $\epsilon > N$,

$$\int_{(1-\epsilon)\mathbb{D}} |R_\epsilon f^2(z + \epsilon)|^{1+2\epsilon} dv(z + \epsilon) \leq \epsilon^{1+2\epsilon} \|1 + \epsilon\|_{L_\mu^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \|f^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon}. \tag{10}$$

Let $v_{(1-\epsilon)} = v \setminus_{\mathbb{D} \setminus (1-\epsilon)\mathbb{D}}$. By (7), Lemmas 3 and 4, the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{D} \setminus (1-\epsilon)\mathbb{D}} |R_\epsilon f^2(z + \epsilon)|^{1+2\epsilon} dv(z + \epsilon) &= \int_{\mathbb{D}} |R_\epsilon f^2(z + \epsilon)|^{1+2\epsilon} dv_{(1-\epsilon)}(z + \epsilon) \\ &\lesssim \|R_\epsilon f^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \sup_{1+\epsilon} \frac{v_{(1-\epsilon)}(S(1+\epsilon))}{\omega(S(1+\epsilon))^{\frac{1+2\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}}} \\ &\lesssim \|R_\epsilon f^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \sup_{\epsilon > 0} \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(\varphi_r(z)) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} \|(1 + \epsilon)(z)\|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z). \end{aligned}$$

$$\lesssim \|f^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \sup_{\epsilon>0} \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(\varphi_r(z)) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} \|(1+\epsilon)(z)\|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z). \tag{11}$$

Letting $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$, by (8)-(11), the researcher gets

$$\|(1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}\|_{e, L_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \lesssim \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(\varphi_r(z)) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} \|(1+\epsilon)(z)\|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z) + \epsilon^{1+2\epsilon} \|1+\epsilon\|_{L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon}.$$

Since ϵ is arbitrary, by letting $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$, the researcher obtains

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}\|_{e, L_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \\ & \lesssim \limsup_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(\varphi_r(z)) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} \|(1+\epsilon)(z)\|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z). \end{aligned}$$

Lower estimate of $\|(1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}\|_{e, L_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon}$.

Assume that $K: A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}$ is compact. By Lemmas 2 and 5.

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left\| KF_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)} \right\|_{A_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}} = 0 \text{ then}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}} \gtrsim \limsup_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left\| ((1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r} - \right. \\ & \left. K)F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)} \right\|_{L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}} \geq \limsup_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left\| (1+\epsilon)\varphi_r F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)} \right\|_{L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}} - \\ & \limsup_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left\| KF_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)} \right\|_{L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}} \\ & = \limsup_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left\| (1+\epsilon)\varphi_r F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)} \right\|_{L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the researcher gets

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| (1 + \epsilon) C_{\varphi_r} \right\|_{e, L_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \geq \limsup_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \\ & \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(\varphi_r(z)) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} \left\| (1 + \epsilon)(z) \right\|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z). \end{aligned}$$

as desired. The proof is complete.

Theorem 3. Assume $(z + \epsilon) \in \widehat{\mathcal{D}}, -1 \leq \frac{\epsilon}{2} < \epsilon < 0, (1 + \epsilon): \mathbb{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is a measurable function, φ_r is an analytic self-map of $\mathcal{D}$, and μ is a positive Borel measure on $\mathbb{D}$. Then the following statements are equivalent.

- (i) $(1 + \epsilon)\varphi_r: A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}$ is bounded;
- (ii) $(1 + \epsilon)\varphi_r: A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}$ is bounded;
- (iii) $\Psi_{(1+\epsilon)\varphi_r}^{-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon}(1 + \epsilon) \in L_{z+\epsilon}^{-\frac{1}{\epsilon}-1}$ for all $-\frac{1}{2} + 3\epsilon$ large enough;
- (iv) $\Psi_{(1+\epsilon)\varphi_r}^{-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon}(1 + \epsilon) \in L_{z+\epsilon}^{-\frac{1}{\epsilon}-1}$ for some $-\frac{1}{2} + 3\epsilon$ large enough.

Moreover, if $-\frac{1}{2} + 3\epsilon$ is fixed,

$$\left\| (1 + \epsilon) C_{\varphi_r} \right\|_{L_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} \approx \left\| \Psi_{-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon} \right\|_{L_{z+\epsilon}^{-\frac{1}{\epsilon}-1}} \tag{12}$$

Here,

$$\Psi_{(1+\epsilon)\varphi_r}^{-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon}(1 + \epsilon) = \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(\varphi_r(z)) \right|^{1+2\epsilon} \left\| (1 + \epsilon)(z) \right\|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z).$$

Proof. Let $v(F - C) = \int_{\varphi^{-1}(F-C)} |(1 + \epsilon)(z)|^{1+2\epsilon} d\mu(z)$ for al Borel set $(F - C)$. By (6), the researcher has

$$\left\| (1 + \epsilon) C_r f^2 \right\|_{L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon} = \|f^2\|_{L_{\nu}^{1+2\epsilon}}^{1+2\epsilon}.$$

So, $(1 + \epsilon)\varphi_r: A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}$ is bounded (compact) if and only if $Id: A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\nu}^{1+2\epsilon}$ is bounded (compact). By (26) in [10] and Theorem 3 in [15], the researcher has (i) $\Leftrightarrow$ (ii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (iii) and (12). Since $1 - |1 + \epsilon| \leq$

$|1 - \overline{1 + \epsilon z}|$ holds for all $(1 + \epsilon), z \in \mathbb{D}$, the researcher gets (iii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (iv). The proof is complete.

Remark 2. Suppose all of the $(1 + \epsilon), (1 + 2\epsilon), \mu, (z + \epsilon), (1 + \epsilon), \varphi_r$ meet the conditions of the Theorem 3 and v is defined as in the proof of Theorem 3. For all $(1 + \epsilon) \in \mathbb{D} \setminus \{0\}$ and $1 < \epsilon < 0$, let

$$\Gamma(1 + \epsilon) = \left\{ z \in \mathbb{D} : |\arg z - \arg(1 + \epsilon)| < \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{|z|}{|1 + \epsilon|} \right) \right\}$$

$$T(1 + \epsilon) = z \in \mathbb{D} : \{(1 + \epsilon) \in \Gamma(z)\}, \Delta(1 + \epsilon), (1 - \epsilon) = \left\{ z \in \mathbb{D} : \left| \frac{(1 + \epsilon) - z}{1 - \overline{1 + \epsilon z}} \right| < 1 - \epsilon \right\},$$

and

$$Q(z) = \int_{\Gamma} (z) \frac{dv(\xi)}{\omega(T(\xi))}, M_{\omega}(v(z)) \sup_{z \in S(1 + \epsilon)} \frac{v(S(1 + \epsilon))}{\omega(S(1 + \epsilon))}, \Phi_{(1 - \epsilon)}(z) = \int_{\Gamma(z)} \frac{v(\Delta(1 + \epsilon), (1 - \epsilon))}{\omega(T(z))} \frac{dA(z)}{(1 - |z|)^2}.$$

By [15, Theorem 3], for any fixed $-\frac{1}{2} + 3\epsilon$ and $1 - \epsilon$, the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned} \|(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+2\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}} &\approx \|Id\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+2\epsilon} \rightarrow L_{\mu}^{1+2\epsilon}} \approx \left\| \Psi_{-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon} \right\|_{L_{z+\epsilon}^{\frac{1}{\epsilon}-1}} \approx \\ &\|M_{\omega}(z)\|_{L_{z+\epsilon}^{\frac{1}{\epsilon}-1}} \approx \|Q\|_{L_{z+\epsilon}^{\frac{1}{\epsilon}-1}} \approx \|\Phi_{(1-\epsilon)}\|_{L_{z+\epsilon}^{\frac{1}{\epsilon}-1}}. \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Using (26) in [10], the researcher knows that all the all the $\omega(S(1 + \epsilon))$ and $\omega(T(1 + \epsilon))$ in (12) and (13) can be exchanged.

Theorem 4. Assume $(z + \epsilon) \in \mathcal{D}$, satisfying $\int_0^1 \left(\log \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon} \right)^2 (z + \epsilon)(1 + \epsilon)d(1 + \epsilon) < \infty$,

$-1 < \epsilon < \infty, (1 + \epsilon): \mathbb{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is a measurable function, φ_r is an analytic self-map of $\mathbb{D}$. if $(1 + \epsilon)\varphi_r: A_{z+\epsilon}^2 \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^2$ is compact, then $(1 + \epsilon)\varphi_r \in S_{(1+\epsilon)}(A_{z+\epsilon}^2)$ if and only if

$$\int_{\mathbb{D}} \left(\frac{\sigma(\Delta(z(1-\epsilon)))}{(z+\epsilon)_*(z)} \right)^{\frac{1+\epsilon}{2}} \frac{dA(z)}{1-2|z|^2+|z|^4} < \infty$$

For some (equivalently for all) $1 < \epsilon < 0$. Moreover, the researcher has

$$|(1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}|_{1+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \approx \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left(\frac{\sigma(\Delta(z(1-\epsilon)))}{(z+\epsilon)_*(z)} \right)^{\frac{1+\epsilon}{2}} \frac{dA(z)}{1-2|z|^2+|z|^4}.$$

Here $\sigma(F-C) = \int_{\varphi^{-1}(F-C)} |(1+\epsilon)(z)|^2 (z+\epsilon) dA(z)$ for all Borel set $(F-C) \subset \mathbb{D}$, and $|\cdot|_{1+\epsilon}$ is the norm of p-Schatten class of $A_{z+\epsilon}^2$.

Proof. For all $f^2, g^2 \in A_{z+\epsilon}^2$, the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned} \langle (1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}^* 1 + \epsilon \rangle_{\varphi_r} f^2, g^2 \rangle_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2} &= \langle (1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r} f^2, (1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r} g^2 \rangle_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2} = \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{D}} f^2 \varphi(z) \overline{g^2 \varphi(z)} |(1+\epsilon)(z)|^2 (z+\epsilon)(z) dA(z) = \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{D}} f^2(\zeta) \overline{g^2(\xi)} d\sigma(\xi) \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

Suppose $B_z^{z+\epsilon}(\xi)$ is the reproducing Kernel of $A_{z+\epsilon}^2$, that is,

$$f^2(z) = \langle f^2, B_z^{z+\epsilon} \rangle_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2} = \int_{\mathbb{D}} f^2(\xi) \overline{B_z^{z+\epsilon}(\xi)} (z+\epsilon)(\xi) dA(\xi).$$

Consider the Toeplitz operator,

$$T_{\sigma} f^2(z) = \int_{\mathbb{D}} f^2(\eta) \overline{B_z^{z+\epsilon}(\eta)} d\sigma(\eta).$$

Since $z+\epsilon$ is radial, by [11, section 4.1], polynomials are dense in $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ for all $-1 < \epsilon < \infty$. So if $f^2, g^2 \in A_{z+\epsilon}^2$, there are two polynomial sequences $\{f_{(1+\epsilon)}^2\}_{\epsilon=0}^{\infty}$ such that

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow \infty} \|f^2 - f_{(1+\epsilon)}^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2} = 0, \text{ and } \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow \infty} \|g^2 - g_{(1+\epsilon)}^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2} = 0.$$

Since $(1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}: A_{z+\epsilon}^2 \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^2$ is compact, by Theorem 1 and lemma 3, the researcher has

$$\|(1+\epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2 \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^2}^2 \approx \sup_{(1+\epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left| F_{(1+\epsilon)^2, (-\frac{1}{2}+3\epsilon)}(z) \right|^2 d\sigma(z) \approx$$

$$\sup_{(1 + \epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}} \frac{\sigma(S(1+\epsilon))}{\omega(S(1+\epsilon))} < \infty.$$

Then, $Id: A_{\omega}^2 \rightarrow A_{\sigma}^2$ and $Id: A_{\omega}^1 \rightarrow A_{\sigma}^1$ are bounded by Lemma 3. So, the researcher has

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|g^2 - g_k^2\|_{A_{\sigma}^2} = 0.$$

For any $h^2 \in H^{\infty} \subset A_{z+\epsilon}^1$, letting $M = \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} |h(z)|$, by [16] (see also [14, Theorem 1]), there exist a $C = C(h^2, 1 + \epsilon, \varphi_r, z + \epsilon)$ such that

$$|T_{\sigma} h^2(z)| \leq M \int_{\mathbb{D}} |B_z^{z+\epsilon}(\eta)| d\sigma(\eta) \leq M, \|Id\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^1 \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^1} \|B_z^{z+\epsilon}\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^1} \leq C \log \frac{e}{1-|z|}.$$

Therefore,

$$\|T_{\sigma} h^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2}^2 \leq \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left(\log \frac{e}{1-|z|}\right)^2 (z + \epsilon)(z) dA(z) < \infty.$$

That is say, $T_{\sigma} h^2 \in A_{z+\epsilon}^2$.

Since $g_{1+\epsilon}^2 \in A_{z+\epsilon}^2 = (A_{z+\epsilon}^2)^*$, for any $(1 + \epsilon) \in \mathbb{N}$, by Lemma 11 of [16],

$$\langle T_{\sigma} f_{(1+\epsilon)}^2, g^2 \rangle_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2} = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \langle T_{\sigma} f_{(1+\epsilon)}^2, g_k^2 \rangle_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2} = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \langle f_{(1+\epsilon)}^2, g_k^2 \rangle_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2} = \int_{\mathbb{D}} f_{(1+\epsilon)}^2(\eta) \overline{g^2(\eta)} d\sigma(\eta). \tag{15}$$

Since g^2 is arbitrary, by (14) and (15), the researcher has

$$T_{\sigma} f_{(1+\epsilon)} = (1 + \epsilon) C_{\varphi_r}^*(1 + \epsilon) C_{\varphi_r} f_{(1+\epsilon)}. \tag{16}$$

For any fixed $z_0 = \mathbb{D}$, when $|z - z_0| < \frac{1+|z_0|}{2}$, by Hölder inequality and [16, Lemma 6], the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned} |T_{\sigma} f^2(z) - T_{\sigma} f_{(1+\epsilon)}^2(z)| &\leq \int_{\mathbb{D}} |f^2(\eta) - f_{(1+\epsilon)}^2(\eta)| |B_z^{z+\epsilon}(\eta)| d\sigma(\eta) \\ &\lesssim \sup_{|z| < (|z_0| + 1) / 2} \frac{1}{\omega(S(z))} \sqrt{\sigma(\mathbb{D})} \|f^2 - f_n^2\|_{A_{\sigma}^2}. \end{aligned}$$

So, the researcher obtains $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} T_\mu f_{1+\epsilon}^2(z) = T_\mu f^2(z)$ for all $z \in \mathbb{D}$. Using (16), the researcher has

$$T_\sigma = (1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}^* (1 + \epsilon)\varphi_r.$$

By [20, Theorem 1.26], when $\epsilon > 0$, $(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r} \in S_{(1+\epsilon)}(A_{z+\epsilon}^2)$ if and only if $((1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r})^*(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r} \in S_{\frac{1+\epsilon}{2}}(A_{z+\epsilon}^2)$. By [16, Theorem 3] (or [13, Theorem 1]), $T_\sigma \in S_{\frac{1+\epsilon}{2}}(A_{z+\epsilon}^2)$ if and only if

$$\int_{\mathbb{D}} \left(\frac{\sigma(\Delta(z, 1-\epsilon))}{(z+\epsilon)_*(z)} \right)^{\frac{1+\epsilon}{2}} \frac{dA(z)}{(1-|z|^2)^2} < \infty,$$

For some (equivalently for all) $0 < r < 1$. Moreover,

$$\left| ((1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}) \right|_{1+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} = |T_\sigma|_{\frac{1+\epsilon}{2}}^{\frac{1+\epsilon}{2}} = \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left(\frac{\sigma(\Delta(z, 1-\epsilon))}{(z+\epsilon)_*(z)} \right)^{\frac{1+\epsilon}{2}} \frac{dA(z)}{(1-|z|^2)^2}.$$

The proof is complete.

Theorem 5. Suppose $0 < \epsilon < \infty$, $(z + \epsilon) \in \mathcal{R}$, φ_r is a finite Blaschke product and $(1 + \epsilon) \in A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$. If $(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}$ is bounded on $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$, then $(1 + \epsilon) \in H^\infty(\mathbb{D})$.

Proof. By [14, corollary 7], the researcher has $(A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon})^* \approx A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}$ where $\frac{1}{1+\epsilon} + \frac{1}{(1+\epsilon)'} = 1$. Let $B_z^{z+\epsilon}(\xi)$ be the reproducing kernel of $A_{z+\epsilon}^2$. By

[16, Lemma 6], $B_z^{z+\epsilon} \in H^\infty \subset A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}$. Since $(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}$ is bounded on $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$, so is $((1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r})^*$ on $A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}$. For all $f^2 \in A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$, the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{\langle (1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}^* B_z^{z+\epsilon}, f^2 \rangle_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2}} &= \overline{\langle B_z^{z+\epsilon}, (1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r} f^2 \rangle_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2}} = \\ &= \overline{(1 + \epsilon)(z) f^2(C_{\varphi_r}(z))} \\ &= \overline{(1 + \epsilon)(z)} \langle B_{\varphi_r(z)}^{z+\epsilon}, f^2 \rangle_{A_{z+\epsilon}^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$(1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}^* B_z^{z+\epsilon} = \overline{(1 + \epsilon)(z)} B_{\varphi_r(z)}^{z+\epsilon}.$$

So,

$$|(1 + \epsilon)(z)| \left\| B_{\varphi_r(z)}^{z+\epsilon} \right\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}} = \overline{\|(1 + \epsilon)(z) B_{\varphi_r}^{z+\epsilon}\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}}} = \|(1 + \epsilon) C_{\varphi_r}^* B_{z+\epsilon}^{z+\epsilon}\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}} \leq \|(1 + \epsilon) C_{\varphi_r}^*\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}} \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}. \left\| B_{\varphi_r}^{z+\epsilon} \right\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}}$$

Let $M = \|(1 + \epsilon) C_{\varphi_r}^*\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}} \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}$. By

[16, Theorem C], the researcher has $\left\| B_{\varphi_r(z)}^{z+\epsilon} \right\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}} \leq$

$$M^{(1+\epsilon)'} \left(\frac{\left\| B_{z+\epsilon}^{z+\epsilon} \right\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}}}{\left\| B_{\varphi_r(z)}^{z+\epsilon} \right\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{(1+\epsilon)'}}} \right)^{(1+\epsilon)'} \approx M^{(1+\epsilon)'} \left(\frac{(z+\epsilon)(S(\varphi_r(z)))}{(z+\epsilon)(S(z))} \right)^{(1+\epsilon)'} - 1. \tag{17}$$

$$\text{Suppose } \varphi_r = z^m \prod_{k=1}^{\epsilon} \frac{|(1+\epsilon)_k| (1+\epsilon)_{k-z}}{(1+\epsilon)_k 1 - (1+\epsilon)_z}$$

Let

$$c = \max\{|(1 + \epsilon)_k| : k = 1, 2, \dots, \epsilon\}, \text{ and } d = \min\{|(1 + \epsilon)_k| : k = 1, 2, \dots, \epsilon\}.$$

As in the proof of [2, Lemma 2.1], for $c < |z| < 1$, the researcher has

$$\frac{1 - |\varphi_r(z)|^2}{1 - |z|^2} \leq m + 2n \frac{1+d}{1-d}.$$

By Lemma 1, there are $0 < \epsilon < \infty$ and $0 < \delta < 1$, such that $\frac{(z+\epsilon)_*(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^{(1+\epsilon)}}$ is increasing on $[\delta, 1[$. Let

$$r_0 = \inf\{r : r > \max\{c, \delta\} \text{ and } |\varphi_r(z)| \geq \delta \text{ for all } |z| = r\}.$$

Then $r_0 = (0, 1)$. Obviously, the researcher has

$$\sup_{|z| \leq r_0} \frac{(z+\epsilon)(S(\varphi_r))}{(z+\epsilon)(S(z))} < \infty. \tag{18}$$

When $|z| > r_0$, by (3), the researcher has

$$\frac{(z+\epsilon)(S(\varphi_r))}{(z+\epsilon)(S(z))} \approx \frac{(z+\epsilon)_*(\varphi_r(z))}{(z+\epsilon)_*(z)}.$$

So, if $|\varphi_r(z)| < |z|$,

$$\frac{(z+\epsilon)_*(\varphi_r(z))}{(z+\epsilon)_*(z)} = \frac{\frac{(z+\epsilon)_*(\varphi_r(z))}{(1-|\varphi_r(z)|^{1+\epsilon})} \frac{(1-|\varphi_r(z)|^{1+\epsilon})}{(1-|z|^{1+\epsilon})}}{\frac{(z+\epsilon)_*(z)}{(1-|z|^{1+\epsilon})}} \lesssim \left(m + 2\epsilon \frac{1+d}{1-d}\right)^{1+\epsilon}. \tag{19}$$

If $|z| \leq |\varphi_r(z)| < 1$, by Lemma 1, the researcher gets

$$\frac{(z+\epsilon)_*(\varphi_r(z))}{(z+\epsilon)_*(z)} \approx \frac{(1-|\varphi_r(z)| \int_{|\varphi_r(z)|}^1 |\varphi_r(z)|^{(z+\epsilon)(1+\epsilon)d(1+\epsilon)})}{(1-|z| \int_{|z|}^1 (z+\epsilon)(1+\epsilon)d(1+\epsilon))} \lesssim m + 2\epsilon \frac{1+d}{1-d}. \tag{20}$$

Therefore, by (17)-(20),the researcher obtains $(1 + \epsilon) \in H^\infty$. The proof is complete.

To state and show the next result see[21], we introduce a set. Let $0 < \epsilon < \infty$, $(z + \epsilon) \in \mathcal{R}$ and φ_r be an analytic self- map of $\mathbb{D}$. The researcher defines

$$X := \{(1 + \epsilon) \in H(\mathbb{D}): (1 + \epsilon)C_{\varphi_r}(A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}) \subset A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}\}.$$

Theorem 6. Let $0 < \epsilon < \infty$ and φ_r be an analytic self- map of $\mathbb{D}$. Suppose $(z + \epsilon) \in \mathcal{R}$ such that

(i) $\widehat{z + \epsilon} (\varphi_{(1+\epsilon)}(1 - \epsilon)) \widehat{z + \epsilon} (1 - \epsilon) \lesssim \widehat{z + \epsilon} (1 + \epsilon)$, for all $1 \leq \epsilon \leq -\epsilon < 0$, here $\varphi_{(1+\epsilon)}(1 - \epsilon) = \frac{2}{\epsilon}$;

(ii) $2A + AB - B > 0$, where $A = \liminf_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\int_{1+\epsilon}^1 (z+\epsilon)(1+\epsilon)d(1+\epsilon)}{\epsilon(z+\epsilon)(1+\epsilon)}$ and

$$B = \limsup_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\int_{1+\epsilon}^1 (z + \epsilon)(1 + \epsilon)d(1 + \epsilon)}{\epsilon(z + \epsilon)(1 + \epsilon)}.$$

If $X = H^\infty$, then φ_r is a finite Blaschke product.

Proof. By [13, proposition 18], for any $(z + \epsilon) \in \mathbb{D}$ and φ_r is an analytic self- map of $\mathbb{D}$, $\varphi_r: A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ is bounded. So, for any $(1 + \epsilon) \in X$, the researcher defines $\|1 + \epsilon\|_X = \|(1 + \epsilon)(\varphi_r)\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}$. Let $\{(1 + \epsilon)_\epsilon\}$ be a Cauchy sequence in X . Then $\{(1 + \epsilon)_\epsilon C_{\varphi_r}\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in $B(A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon})$. Here, $B(A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon})$ means the set of bounded operations on $A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$. So, there exists a $T \in B(A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon})$, such that $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow \infty} ((1 + \epsilon)_\epsilon C_{\varphi_r}) = T$. Since $f^2(z) = 1 \in A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$.

$$(1+\epsilon) := T(1) \in A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}, \text{ and } \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow \infty} \|(1+\epsilon)_\epsilon - (1+\epsilon)\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}} = 0$$

Therefore, for all $f^2 \in A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$,

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow \infty} (1+\epsilon)_\epsilon(z) f^2(\varphi_r)(z) = (1+\epsilon)(z) f^2(\varphi_r)(z).$$

Since $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow \infty} \|(1+\epsilon)_\epsilon \varphi_r f^2 - T f^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}} = 0$,

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow \infty} (1+\epsilon)_\epsilon f^2 \varphi_r(z) = (T f^2)(z).$$

So, the researcher has $T f^2 = (1+\epsilon) C_{\varphi_r} f^2$ for all $f^2 \in A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$. There fore $(1+\epsilon) \in X$. That is to say, X is complete under the norm $\|\cdot\|_X$.

Since $X = H^\infty, C_{\varphi_r} \in B(A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon})$. Then for all $(1+\epsilon) \in X, \|1+\epsilon\|_X \leq \|1+\epsilon\|_{H^\infty} \|C_{\varphi_r}\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}$. By Inverse Mapping Theorem, $\|1+\epsilon\|_X \leq \|1+\epsilon\|_{H^\infty}$.

By $(z+\epsilon) \in \mathcal{R}$, the researcher has $AB > 0$. Therefore $\frac{2+B}{B} > \frac{1}{A}$. So, there exists $0 < \epsilon < A$ such that $\frac{2}{B+\epsilon} + 1 + \frac{1}{A-\epsilon} > 0$.

Let $(1+\epsilon) = \frac{1-(B+\epsilon)}{B+\epsilon}$ and $(1+\epsilon) = \frac{1-(A-\epsilon)}{A-\epsilon}$. Then $3+\epsilon > 0$. By the proof of [11, Lemma 1.1], there is a $0 < \delta < 1$ such that

$$\frac{(z+\epsilon)(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^{1+\epsilon}} \text{ is essential decreasing on } [\delta, 1[\text{ and } \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{(z+\epsilon)(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^{1+\epsilon}} = 0;$$

And

$$\frac{(z+\epsilon)(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^{1+\epsilon}} \text{ is essential decreasing on } [\delta, 1[\text{ and } \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{(z+\epsilon)(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^{1+\epsilon}} = \infty.$$

Let

$$\mu(z) = \begin{cases} (z+\epsilon)(z), & \delta \leq |z| < 1; \\ \frac{(z+\epsilon)(\delta)(1-|z|)^{1+\epsilon}}{(1-\delta)^{1+\epsilon}}, & |z| < \delta. \end{cases}$$

Then it is easy to check that the following statements hold.

(i) $\frac{\mu(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^{1+\epsilon}}$ is essential decreasing on $[0,1[$ and $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\mu(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^{1+\epsilon}} = 0$;

- (ii) $\frac{\mu(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^{1+\epsilon}}$ is essential decreasing on $[0,1[$ and $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\mu(1-\epsilon)}{\epsilon^{1+\epsilon}} = \infty$;
- (iii) $\mu \in \mathcal{R}, A = \liminf_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\int_{1+\epsilon}^1 \mu(1+\epsilon)d(1+\epsilon)}{\epsilon\mu(1+\epsilon)}$ and $B = \limsup_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\int_{1+\epsilon}^1 \mu(1+\epsilon)d(1+\epsilon)}{\epsilon\mu(1+\epsilon)}$;
- (iv) $\|f^2\|_{A_{\mu}^{1+\epsilon}} \approx \|f^2\|_{A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}$ and $\hat{\mu}(\varphi_{(1+\epsilon)}(1-\epsilon))\hat{\mu}(1-\epsilon) \lesssim \hat{\mu}(1+\epsilon)$, for all $1 \leq \epsilon < 0$.

Therefore, without loss of generality, let $\delta = 0$. So, the researcher has

$$\frac{(z+\epsilon)(\varphi_{r(z+\epsilon)}(z))}{(z+\epsilon)(z)} = \frac{\frac{(z+\epsilon)(\varphi_{r(z+\epsilon)}(z))}{1-|\varphi_{r(z+\epsilon)}(z)|^{1+\epsilon}}}{\frac{(z+\epsilon)(z)}{1-|z|^{1+\epsilon}}} \lesssim \left(\frac{1-|\varphi_{r(z+\epsilon)}(z)|^2}{1-|z|} \right)^{1+\epsilon}, \text{ when } |\varphi_r(z)| > |z|,$$

And

$$\frac{(z+\epsilon)(\varphi_{r(z+\epsilon)}(z))}{(z+\epsilon)(z)} = \frac{\frac{(z+\epsilon)(\varphi_{r(z+\epsilon)}(z))}{1-|\varphi_{r(z+\epsilon)}(z)|^{\frac{1}{2}+2\epsilon}}}{\frac{(z+\epsilon)(z)}{1-|z|^{\frac{1}{2}+2\epsilon}}} \lesssim \left(\frac{1-|\varphi_{r(z+\epsilon)}(z)|^2}{1-|z|} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}+2\epsilon}, \text{ when } |\varphi_r(z)| \leq |z|,$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(z+\epsilon)(\varphi_{r(z+\epsilon)}(z))}{(z+\epsilon)(z)} &\lesssim \left(\frac{1-|\varphi_{r(z+\epsilon)}(z)|^2}{1-|z|^2} \right)^{1+\epsilon} + \left(\frac{1-|\varphi_{r(z+\epsilon)}(z)|^2}{1-|z|^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}+2\epsilon} = \\ &= \left(\frac{1-|z+\epsilon|^2}{|1-(z+\bar{\epsilon})(z)^2|} \right)^{1+\epsilon} + \\ &\left(\frac{1-|z+\epsilon|^2}{|1-(z+\bar{\epsilon})(z)^2|} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}+2\epsilon}. \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Let $\alpha = \frac{6+2\epsilon}{1+2\epsilon}$ and $(1+\epsilon)_{(z+\epsilon)}(z) = \left(\frac{1}{1-(z+\bar{\epsilon})(z)} \right)^\alpha$. Then $\|(1+\epsilon)_{z+\epsilon}\|_\infty^{1+\epsilon} = \frac{1}{(1-|z+\epsilon|)^{6+2\epsilon}}$. For all $f^2 \in A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$, by (21), the researcher has

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \| (1 + \epsilon)_{z+\epsilon} C_{\varphi_r} f^2 \|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}^{1+\epsilon} \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{D}} \frac{1}{|1 - \overline{(z + \epsilon)}z|^{(1+\epsilon)\alpha}} |f^2 \circ \varphi_r(z)|^{1+\epsilon} (z + \epsilon)(z) dA(z) \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{D}} \frac{1}{|1 - \overline{(z + \epsilon)}\varphi_r(z+\epsilon)(z)|^{(1+\epsilon)\alpha}} |f^2 \circ \varphi_r \circ \varphi_{z+\epsilon}(z)|^{1+\epsilon} |\varphi'_{z+\epsilon}(z)|^2 \\
 &\quad \omega(\varphi_{z+\epsilon})(z) dA(z) \\
 &\lesssim \frac{1}{(1 - |z + \epsilon|^2)^{3+\epsilon}} \int_{\mathbb{D}} |f^2 \circ \varphi_r \circ \varphi_{z+\epsilon}(z)|^{1+\epsilon} \left(1 + \left(\frac{1 - |z + \epsilon|^2}{|1 - \overline{(z + \epsilon)}z|^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2} + \epsilon} \right) \omega(z) dA(z) \\
 &\lesssim \frac{1}{(1 - |z + \epsilon|^2)^{\frac{5}{2} + \epsilon}} \int_{\mathbb{D}} |f^2 \circ \varphi_r \circ \varphi_{z+\epsilon}(z)|^{1+\epsilon} \omega(z) dA(z) \\
 &\lesssim \frac{\|f^2\|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}^{1+\epsilon}}{(1 - |z + \epsilon|^2)^{\frac{5}{2} + 2\epsilon} (1 - |\varphi_r(z)|) \widehat{\omega}(\varphi_r(z + \epsilon))}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The last inequality can be got by [13, Proposition 18]. By $|(1 + \epsilon)_{z+\epsilon}|_{\infty} \approx \| (1 + \epsilon)_{z+\epsilon} C_{\varphi_r} \|_{A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}}$, the researcher has

$$\frac{1}{(1 - |z + \epsilon|^2)^{\frac{7}{2}}} \lesssim \frac{1}{(1 - |\varphi_r(z)|) \widehat{\omega}(\varphi_r(z + \epsilon))}.$$

By $\frac{7}{2} + \epsilon > 0$, the researcher has $|\varphi_r(z + \epsilon)| \rightarrow 1$ as $|z + \epsilon| \rightarrow 1$. By Lemma 6. φ_r is a finite Blaschke product. The proof is complete.

By Theorems 5 and 6, for some regular weight ω , $X = H^\infty$ if and only if φ_r is a finite Blaschke product. Here, the researcher gives two examples.

Corollary 7. Let $0 < \epsilon < \infty$, and φ_r be an analytic self-map of $\mathbb{D}$. Suppose ω is either $(1 + \epsilon)$ or $(\frac{1}{2} + 2\epsilon)$.

(a) $\omega(1 - \epsilon) = \epsilon^\alpha \left(\log \frac{e}{\epsilon} \right)^\beta$, $\alpha > -1$ and $\beta \leq 0$;

(b) $\omega(1 - \epsilon) = \exp\left(-\beta \left(\log \frac{e}{\epsilon}\right)^\alpha\right)$, $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ and $\beta > 0$.

Then, $= H^\infty$ if and only if φ_r is a finite Blaschke product.

Proof. By [1, (4.4) and (4.5)], the weights (a) and (b) are regular.

Suppose φ_r is a finite Blaschke product. By [13, Theorem 18], $C_{\varphi_r}: A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon} \rightarrow A_{Z+\epsilon}^{1+\epsilon}$ is bounded. So, $H^\infty \subset X$. By Theorem 5, $X \subset H^\infty$. Therefore, $X = H^\infty$.

Suppose $X = H^\infty$. By Bernouilli-I' Hôpital theorem, both (a) and (b) meet the condition (ii) of Theorem 6. So, if the researcher shows that (a) and (b) meet the condition (i) of Theorem 6, then φ_r is a finite Blaschke product.

Condition (a). When $1 \leq \epsilon \leq 0$, let $\theta = \frac{1-\epsilon}{1+\epsilon}$ and

$$f^2(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) = \log \frac{e(1 - \theta(1 + 2\epsilon + \epsilon^2))}{\epsilon(1 + \theta(1 + \epsilon))} \log \frac{e}{1 - \theta(1 + \epsilon)}, (0 \leq \theta \leq 1, 0 < t < 1).$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & f'_\theta(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) \\ &= - \left(\frac{1 + 2\epsilon + \epsilon^2}{1 - \theta(1 + 2\epsilon + \epsilon^2)} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{1 + \epsilon}{1 + \theta(1 + \epsilon)} \right) \log \frac{e + 1 + \epsilon}{1 - \theta(1 + \epsilon)} \log \frac{e(1 - \theta(1 + 2\epsilon + \epsilon^2))}{\epsilon(1 + \theta(1 + \epsilon))} \end{aligned}$$

Suppose $\epsilon > -1$, and let

$$\begin{aligned} g^2(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) &= \frac{1-\theta(1+\epsilon)}{1+\epsilon} f'_\theta(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) = \log \frac{e(1-\theta(1+2\epsilon+\epsilon^2))}{\epsilon(1+\theta(1+\epsilon))} - \\ & \left(\frac{(1+\epsilon)(1-\theta(1+\epsilon))}{1-\theta(1+\epsilon)} + \frac{1-\theta(1+\epsilon)}{1+\theta(1+\epsilon)} \right) \log \frac{e}{1-\theta(1+\epsilon)}. \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$f'_\theta(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) = -\left(\frac{2(1+2\epsilon+\epsilon^2)}{1-\theta(1+2\epsilon+\epsilon^2)} + \frac{2(1+\epsilon)}{1+\theta(1+\epsilon)}\right) - \frac{(1+\epsilon)^3 - (1+\epsilon)^2}{(1-\theta(1+2\epsilon+\epsilon^2))^2} - \frac{2(1+\epsilon)}{(1-\theta(1+\epsilon))^2} \log \frac{e}{1-\theta(1+\epsilon)} = \frac{1}{((1+\theta(1+\epsilon))^2)} \left(\frac{((1+\theta(1+\epsilon))^2)}{((1+\theta(1+\epsilon))^2)} h^2(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) \right) + 2(1 + \epsilon)k^2(\theta, 1 + \epsilon),$$

Where

$$h^2(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) = (1 + \epsilon)^2 - (1 + \epsilon)^3 \log \frac{e}{1-\theta(1+\epsilon)} - (2 + 4\epsilon + 2\epsilon^2)(1 - \theta(1 + 2\epsilon + \epsilon^2))$$

and

$$k^2(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) = \log \frac{e}{1-\theta(1+\epsilon)} - (1 + \theta(1 + \epsilon)).$$

Since

$$h'_\theta(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) = \frac{(1+\epsilon)^3 + (1+\epsilon)^4 - 2\theta(1+\epsilon)^5}{1-\theta(1+\epsilon)} > 0, h^{2'}_\theta(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) = (1 + \epsilon) \left(-1 + \frac{1}{1 - \theta(1 + \epsilon)} \right) > 0,$$

the researcher has

$$G(\theta, 1 + \epsilon): (1 + \theta(1 + \epsilon))^2 g'_\theta(\theta, 1 + \epsilon)$$

Is increasing on $[0, 1]$ about θ . Since $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} G(I, 1 + \epsilon) = +\infty$, there exists a $0 < t < 1$ such that $G(I, 1 + \epsilon) > 0$, for all $(1 + \epsilon) \in (\tau, 1)$. If $(1 + \epsilon) \in (\tau, 1)$, by $G(0, 1 + \epsilon) < 0$, there is a

$0 < \nu(1 + \epsilon) < 1$, such that

$$G(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) < 0, \text{ when } 0 \leq \theta < \nu(1 + \epsilon),$$

and

$$G(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) > 0, \text{ when } \nu(1 + \epsilon) < \theta \leq 1.$$

Since

$g'_\theta(\theta, 1 + \epsilon) = \frac{G(\theta, 1 + \epsilon)}{((1 + \theta(1 + \epsilon))^2)}$, when $(1 + \epsilon) \in (\tau, 1)$, $g(\theta, 1 + \epsilon)$ is decreasing on $(0, v(1 + \epsilon))$ and increasing on $(v(1 + \epsilon), 1]$. Since

$$g(0, 1 + \epsilon) = \log \frac{e}{\epsilon} - (2 + \epsilon) > 0, \text{ and } g(1, 1 + \epsilon) = \frac{1}{2 + \epsilon} \left(2 + \epsilon - \log \frac{e}{\epsilon} \right) < 0.$$

So there is a $0 < \mu(1 + \epsilon) < 1$ for every $(1 + \epsilon) \in (\tau, 1)$, such that, $f^2 = f^2(\theta, 1 + \epsilon)$ is increasing on $[0, \mu(1 + \epsilon))$ and decreasing on $(\mu(1 + \epsilon), 1]$. Since $f^2(0, 1 + \epsilon) = f^2(1, 1 + \epsilon)$

$$= \frac{e}{\epsilon},$$

$$\frac{f^2(\theta, 1 + \epsilon)}{\log \frac{e}{\epsilon}} \geq 1, \text{ when } (1 + \epsilon) \in (\tau, 1) \text{ and } 0 \leq \theta \leq 1.$$

It is obvious that

$$(1 + \epsilon) \in [0, \tau], \theta \in [0, 1] = \frac{f^2(\theta, 1 + \epsilon)}{\log \frac{e}{\epsilon}} > 0.$$

Therefore, the researcher has

$$C_1 := \inf_{1 \leq \epsilon \leq 0} \frac{\log \frac{e\epsilon^2}{-2\epsilon + \epsilon^2} \log \frac{e}{\epsilon}}{\log \frac{e}{\epsilon}} > 0.$$

So, when $\alpha > -1, \beta \leq 0$ and $(1 - \epsilon) = \epsilon^\alpha \left(\log \frac{e}{\epsilon} \right)^\beta$, the researcher has

$$\frac{\omega(\varphi_{(1+\epsilon)}(1 - \epsilon))\omega(1 - \epsilon)}{\omega(1 + \epsilon)} \approx \left(\frac{\log \frac{e\epsilon^2}{-2\epsilon + \epsilon^2} \log \frac{e}{\epsilon}}{\log \frac{e}{\epsilon}} \right)^\beta \leq C_1^\beta.$$

Since $\omega \in \mathcal{R}$, the researcher gets

- [5] Ž. Čučkovič and R. Zhao, Weighted composition operators between different weighed Bergman spaces and different Hardy spaces, *Illinois J. Math.* **51** (2007), 479-498.
- [6] R. Demazeus, Essential norms of weighted composition operators between different Hardy spaces, H^p and H^q for $1 \leq p, q \leq \infty$, *Stud. Math.* **206** (2011), 191-209.
- [7] P. Durean and A. Schuster, Bergman spaces, *Math. Surveys and Monographs*, Vol.100, American Mathematical Society, Providence, Rhode Island, 2004.
- [8] J. Linden Strauss and L. Tzafriri, Classical Banach spaces, *Lecture Notes in Mathematics*, Vol. 338, Springer, Berlin (1973).
- [9] W. Lusky, On generalized Bergman spaces, *Stud. Math.* **119** (1996). 77-99.
- [10] J. Peláez, small weighted Bergman spaces, *Proceedings of the summer school in complex and harmonic analysis, and related topics*, 2016.
- [11] J. Peláez, and J. Rättyä, Weighted Bergman spaces induced by rapidly increasing weights, *Mem. Amer. Math.Soc.* **277** (1066) (2014).
- [12] J. Peláez, and J. Rättyä, Embedding theorems for Bergman spaces via harmonic analysis, *Math Ann.* **362** (2015), 205-239.
- [13] J. Peláez, and J. Rättyä, Trace class criteria for Toeplitz and composition operators on small Bergman space, *Adv. Math.* **293** (2016), 606-643.
- [14] J. Peláez, and J. Rättyä, Two weight inequality for the Bergman projection, *J. Math. Pures. Appl.* **105** (2016), 102-130.
- [15] J. Peláez, and J. Rättyä, and K. Sierra, Embedding Bergman spaces into tent spaces, *Math. Z.* **281** (2015), 1215-1237.
- [16] J. Peláez, and J. Rättyä, and K. Sierra, Berezin transform and Toeplitz operators on Bergman spaces induced by regular weights, *J. Geom. Anal.* **28** (2018), 656-687.
- [17] W. Rudin, *Function Theory in polydisc*, W.A. Benjamin Inc. New York, 1969. [18] L. Zhao and S. Hou, A note on weighted composition operators on the weighted Bergman space, *Acta Math. Sci.* **31** (2015), 947-952.
- [19] K. Zhu, Duality of Bloch spaces and norm convergence of Taylor series, *Mich. Math.* **38** (1991), 89-101. [20] K. Zhu, Operator

Theory in function spaces, 2ed edition, Math. Surveys and Monographs, Vol. **138**, American Mathematical Society: Providence, Rhode Island, 2007.

[21] JUNTAO DU, SONGXIAO LI AND YECHENG SHI, weighted composition operators on weighted Bergman spaces induced by double weights. arXiv preprint arXiv:1811.01385, 2018.